

**BARRIERS AND PATHWAYS FOR ENHANCING ISLAMIC
BANKING ADOPTION IN AFGHANISTAN: A QUALITATIVE
STUDY**

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**Barriers and Pathways for Enhancing Islamic Banking Adoption in
Afghanistan: A Qualitative Study**

By

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ABSTRACT

This study, explores the critical factors affecting the growth of Islamic banking in Afghanistan and the purpose is to explore the barriers and potential pathways for its enhanced adoption. With a qualitative research methodology, data is collected from 10 in-depth interviews with Islamic banking professionals and twenty-five survey responses from consumers. The analysis, guided by thematic coding and supported by NVivo, focused on identifying the barriers to and the enablers of Islamic finance adoption. The findings show that the key obstacles includes Operational and Product Limitations, Lack of Awareness and Misconception, Regulatory and Legal Challenges, Sharia-Compliance and Governance Issues, and Economic and Political Instability. Conversely, the participants also identified opportunities that can lead to improvement in the adoption and enhanced implementation of the Islamic Banking in Afghanistan, this includes but not limited to, Education and awareness strategies, Innovation and product development or tailoring the products to the current market need, Strengthening regulation and oversight through a harmonized board, Digitalization and operational efficiency and Institutional capacity building. This study offers invaluable contribution to Afghanistan's financial sector and specifically to the Islamic Banking sector, this also includes actionable recommendations or strategies of enhanced adoption that aligns with the religious and ethical values of Afghans. Adoption of these strategies will lead to greater financial inclusion and a sustainable banking sector that will benefit government and consumers.

Keywords: Islamic banking, Afghanistan, Theory of Reasoned Action, Theory of Planned Behavior, Consumer Barriers

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AUAF	American University of Afghanistan
CBI	Central Bank of Afghanistan (Da Afghanistan Bank)
IFI	Islamic Financial Institution
IB	Islamic Banking
RQ	Research Question
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
PLS	Profit and Loss Sharing
Riba	Interest (prohibited in Islamic finance)
Shariah	Islamic Law
NVivo	Qualitative Data Analysis Software
Ijarah	Islamic Leasing
Mudarabah	Profit-Sharing Partnership
Musharakah	Joint Venture Partnership
Sukuk	Islamic Bonds
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
TBP	Theory of Planned Behavior
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

According to the the basics of Islamic Sharia law, interest (riba), gambling (maysir), and investing money with companies which deals in forbidden (haram) goods and services are prohibited. In the past few decades, Islamic finance has become widely practiced globally, providing an ethical and faithful (halal) alternative to conventional financial systems.

“The year presented significant challenges, including persistent inflation, geopolitical tensions, rising global debt, and vulnerabilities in commercial real estate. Yet, the global IFSI has shown remarkable resilience, with total assets reaching USD 3.38 trillion¹.” (Islamic Financial Services Board [IFSB], 2023).

In Afghanistan, adopting Islamic finance principles has been integral to the countrys financial landscape, particularly in the post-2001 and post-2021 eras. The Central Bank of Afghanistan (CBI) put together a set of regulations in 2017, a set of rules and regulations for Islamic banking and issued a license to a fully Islamic and Sharia-based bank in 2018, which was called the Islamic Bank of Afghanistan. In addition, in the post-2021 era, which is exclusively based on the Islamic mentality, the Taliban government, according to the Jurist News website,

“The Taliban-led Central Bank of Afghanistan has established a committee to review and amend the Central Bank Law and the Banking Law of Afghanistan. According to the Central Bank, a seven-member committee is set up to study and propose amendments to the Central Bank Law” (Jurist News, 2022, para 1).

Though, the current government led by Talibans which are known for their conservative stance has developed Islamic banking regulations, the financial sectors continuous to face numerous challenges in its practical implementation. In addition, there is lack of enough academic research in this particular area, this study addresses the gap by exploring the obstacles for the adoption of Islamic banking or Islamic finance and the potential pathways for its advancement. The findings are expected to increase the public awareness and understanding of the Islamic banking while also provide invaluable insight for the policymakers to incorporate the recommendations for more effective adoption.

1.2 Research Problem

“Afghanistan faces significant challenges in its financial sector, particularly in providing essential financial and credit services to support its economy. This is compounded by the fact that Afghanistan ranks among the worlds least developed countries, with a gross domestic product (GDP) slightly exceeding \$20 billion as of 2022 and a per capita GDP of only \$507” (UNDP, 2022a) and is reduced to slightly over \$17 billion as of 2023 (World Bank Open Data, 2023) with a notable increase reported by World Bank (World Bank Group, 2025).

Afghanistan currently has an estimated population of approximately 48 million people (Afghanistan Population, n.d.), of which 99.7% identify as Muslim (Muslim Population by Country, n.d.). It is still facing challenges in adopting Islamic Banking for its banking needs. While Sharia-compliant finances align with the ethical and religious values of the population, the adoption remains limited. Afghanistan currently has only one Islamic Bank, which was changed from a conventional bank to a fully fledged Islamic Bank in 2018 according to Tolo News (“First Islamic Bank in Afghanistan Opens for Business,” 2018) and according to the global index

database 2021 report, only 10% of the adults have bank accounts. (World Bank Group, 2022) while the remaining 90% adults are not having any single account in any of the bank.

As the country seeks to re-construct its financial infrastructure in a post-conflict context, understanding the institutional challenges and barriers to an enhanced adoption is essential and required. This research explores both the barriers and potential pathways for strengthening the Islamic or faithful banking in Afghanistan that contributes to more inclusive, culturally relevant and sustainable financial systems.

1.3 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to explore the existing state of Islamic banking in Afghanistan, identify the key challenges, and recommend ways to bridge the gaps for more effective implementation. Specifically, the research:

- Identify key consumer barriers to adopting Islamic Banking products and services in Afghanistan.
- Provide recommendations for enhancing the Islamic Banking adoption in Afghanistan.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What obstacles do consumers in Afghanistan encounter when adopting Islamic banking products and services?

- How can banking institutions in Afghanistan enhance the adoption and effectiveness of Islamic finance products?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study is crucial for Afghanistan economic development as it explores the potential of Islamic finance in addressing financial challenges and promoting sustainable economic growth. It identifies obstacles to the adoption of Islamic Banking and explores potential pathways to solutions.

From a banking perspective, the study provides insights into the challenges faced by financial institutions in implementing Islamic finance products. It help banks develop strategies to improve product offerings, streamline regulatory compliance, and enhance their competitiveness in the financial sector.

This research is significant for customers as it discusses the barriers limiting their access to Islamic Banking services and suggests pathways that improve their experience. This research enable consumers to make informed decisions about their savings and, most importantly, targets those who avoid conventional banking. Furthermore, the research highlights the importance of transparency and trust, urging institutions to improve Shariah governance, which can increase consumer confidence. Ultimately, the findings aim to empower Afghan consumers by supporting the development of ethical, inclusive, and customer-focused Islamic banking services that align with their values and everyday needs.

1.6 Scope of the Research

This study examines current barriers and potential pathways to an enhanced implementation of the Islamic Banking system in Afghanistan. Respondents include bank professionals and consumers. A qualitative research methodology is employed to gain in-depth insights into the subject. While Afghanistan has a diverse cultural and socio-economic landscape, this research does not focus on regional variations in Islamic finance offerings. Additionally, conventional financial institutions that do not provide Shariah-compliant products are excluded from the study.

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

The structure of this thesis is as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the research problem, objectives, and significance. Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature on Barriers and Pathways to an enhanced Islamic Banking Implementation in Afghanistan. Chapter 3 outlines the research methodology used for data collection and analysis. Chapter 4 presents the findings from the data collected and provides an analysis of the current state of Islamic finance in Afghanistan. Chapter 5 discusses the implications of these findings and provides recommendations for improvement with a concise conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the scholarly foundations surrounding the barriers and opportunities in the adoption of Islamic banking products and services in Afghanistan. Drawing upon two relevant significant theories, which are the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TBP), both of which are central to this analysis. The TRA (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) states that an individual's behavior is driven by behavioral intention formed through personal attitude and social pressures. In addition to this, the TBP (Ajzen, 1991) extends the TRA's scope and introduces the perceived behavioral control as a crucial factor that accounts for external barriers and enables the conditions that influence decision-making. These theories provide valuable insight into how Afghan consumers perceive Islamic banking, particularly in the face of religious norms, societal expectations, and institutional limitations.

2.2 Foundational Theories and Their Application

Islamic finance is primarily structured in the principles of Shariah law, which restricts interest (riba), uncertainty (gharar), and gambling (maysir). Several key theoretical frameworks feature Islamic banking:

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), developed by Fishbein & Ajzen (1975), indicates that a person's behavior is primarily influenced by their intentions to perform the

behavior, which is influenced by two main factors: attitude toward the intention and subjective norms.

The attitude is further contingent upon two more factors: behavioral belief and evaluation of the result. In this context, exploring the first contingent of behavioral belief, the adoption of Islamic banking is interest free, easy to use, feel well informed for positive behavior or no difference with the conventional banking system, unable to understand which is lack of awareness and many more that accounts for negative behavior can lead to a change in the behavior. Moreover, the second contingent evaluates the results, which is the self-evaluation of the behavioral belief generated. As an example, will it be interest-free, or will it be easy to use? Etc., the answers to these questions trigger the attitude and subsequently change the intention and behavior.

The subjective norm is also contingent upon normative belief and motivation to comply. The normative belief in this context explores what the norms are around that convince me to adopt Islamic banking, and whether those are acceptable in our society, or is it a normal practice that everyone follows, and the personal motivation to follow what is a normal practice or a norm in the society.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is built upon the TRA by Ajzen (1991) for its notable limitations focusing on an individuals own perception or power of doing or not doing an activity or based on the weight of the other two factors (attitude toward behavior and subjective norm) decides to do or not do an action. The following is the diagram that shows each element of this theory.

Figure 1: TRA and TBP Theories

Source: Adapted from The theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned behavior by I. Ajzen, 2011, in Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology (Vol. 1, pp. 438–459), SAGE Publications. Available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235360939>.

2.2.1 Gaps or Limitations in Theories

Despite their strengths, these theories fail to address the difficulties of introducing Islamic banking in post-conflict nations such as Afghanistan. Additionally, although both theories offer a robust framework for understanding consumer intentions and behavior, both theories assume that individuals have full information and are making rational decisions. However, in Afghanistan, most of the time, the decisions are not based on cost-benefit analysis but on faith and Sharia Law.

2.3 Key Concepts and Definitions

2.3.1 Islamic Banking and Finance

Islamic banking, Islamic finance (Arabic: مصرفية إسلامية masrifīyya islamia), or Sharia-compliant finance, is banking or financing activity that complies with Sharia (Islamic law) and its practical application through the development of Islamic economics (Wikipedia contributors, 2025). According to Islamic Bank of Afghanistan (Islamic Bank of Afghanistan, n.d.)

Murabaha is a particular type of sale where the seller explicitly discloses the cost of the commodity / assets purchased by him, and the expected profit from the sale thereof to the purchaser. In other words, it is a contract where cost of the assets and the expected profit are disclosed by the seller to the potential buyer.

Musharika means Partnership. It is a widely used Islamic banking product in which bank and its customers enter into an association through partnership agreement. In this Islamic mode of financing, each party shares to the capital of the partnership equally or in variation to develop a new project or participate in an on-going project. The profit is divided between the parties with a predetermined method, while losses are shared mutually on a pro-rata basis.

Ijarah (Islamic Leasing) is the most common financing instrument used by Islamic banks all over the world. IBA is currently offering Plant, Machinery and vehicle financing on the basis of Ijarah. Ijarah is a contract whereby Bank transfers right to use of Ijarah Asset to the customer for agreed period with agreed rentals. All the assets will be financed on Ijarah basis which are Shariah Compliant. Following are the common assets for Ijarah financing;

Istisna is a contract of sale of specified items to be manufactured or constructed, with an obligation on the part of the manufacturer or builder (contractor) to deliver them to the Customer upon completion.

Salam facilitates businesses involved in agricultural and industrial production or trade and the like. They need working capital in the form of either cash or goods. Hence, Salam meets immediate needs for liquidity because it gives the seller flexibility in using the sale proceeds (before the commodity is delivered) and the opportunity to arrange for the purchased commodity and its delivery to the buyer at the date of delivery. (p.1)

The above five types of Islamic banking products and services are currently offered by the only Islamic bank of Afghanistan under the government and the banks Sharia board.

2.4 Variations in Interpretation

One of the critical challenges in the adoption and application of Islamic banking practices is the variation in the interpretation of Shariah principles across different schools of Islamic jurisprudence, unlike the conventional financial system, which is governed by universally accepted rules and laws. These various schools, such as Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi, and Hambali, have different views and rulings on certain products such as Ijara (Leasing). Some scholars of the Hanafi School of Thought say that it is not halal, while the Shafi and Hanbali scholars state that it is allowed. For instance, Malaysia adopts a progressive regulatory approach (Laldin, 2008), while some GCC countries tend to be more conservative, including Afghanistan. In addition, due to the lack of enough and qualified Sharia scholars, the regulatory framework remains underdeveloped, which is affecting the credibility and growth of Islamic banking and ultimately influences the overall adoption of Islamic banking.

2.5 Empirical Studies

The following are a few previous studies that mainly focus on the adoption of Islamic banking in different contexts and highlight the barriers and opportunities

In context of Indonesia, where the largest Muslim population exists, the market share of Islamic banks was 6.5% of the total market share as of 2021, Nugraha, Arief, Addinagoro, and Heriyati (2022) has explored the barriers to Islamic banking during the COVID-19 period using a qualitative descriptive approach, interviewing the banking staff via purposive sampling technique. Their thematic analysis shows that many consumers showed a passive resistance, which means they continue to use the conventional banks not because they are opposed to Islamic banking, but because of their perception of high risk, weaker brand image, and limited marketing efforts. This study concludes that the adoption of Islamic banks must address the awareness, misconceptions, and increase intense marketing.

In another study that was conducted in Afghanistan, where Islamic banking remains new and financial inclusion is still low, Naseri and Sharofiddin (2021) conducted the first empirical study on the adoption of Islamic banking, which is focused on Herat province. The researcher has applied Rogers Diffusion of Innovation theory to examine what factors influences the consumer perception about Islamic banking. Using a quantitative approach with more than 300 responses and multiple regression analysis, the study reveals that product knowledge, perceived relative advantage and religiosity has positive impact on adoption. Those consumer with product knowledge has noticed benefits of choosing Islamic banking over the conventional banking and upholding their religious values. The study highlights that under-banked and culturally sincere societies, education and awareness plays key role in the adoption. The author recommends

awareness campaigns, education and supportive government regulations for a stronger sector development.

In Pakistan, where Islamic banking has coexisted with conventional banking for over 15 years and yet holds a fair market share, Yaseen and Kamran (2019) investigated why many Muslims continue to use conventional banking over Islamic banking. The researchers have used a qualitative approach via semi-structured interviews with 50 conventional banking users. The study reveals a limited understanding of Islamic banking principles, doubts over the authenticity of sharia-compliance, and they have also reported inferior service quality with the accessibility of conventional banking over Islamic banking. The researchers suggest improved service quality, ensuring the authenticity, and upholding the standards of Shariah compliance.

According to Boubker, Douayri, and Ouajdouni (2021), factors that influence micro-business owners to adopt Islamic banking are the obligation and perceived reputation of Islamic financial institutions, which positively impact the attitude toward Islamic finance adoption. This is the finding of the research conducted in Morocco, and data were collected through a face-to-face questionnaire from micro-entrepreneurs. This study concludes that positive perception, building institutional trust, leveraging social networks, and simplifying the financing process are crucial for increasing the adoption of Islamic banking in Morocco.

According to Mahdzan, Zaiudin, and Au (2017), these three individuals investigated the level of understanding of Islamic banking principles, which can influence the adoption in Malaysia. The study was conducted or motivated by concerns that the consumers might not fully understand the unique features of Islamic financial services. Through a structured survey of 200 participants and using regression techniques, they evaluated the relationship between knowledge

level and adoption behavior. The findings of the study indicate that consumers had a below-average understanding, which has significantly affected the adoption. This study shows the importance of literacy and consumer education, which is key to boosting the Islamic banking adoption.

Osaretin (2023) has conducted a quantitative study with 400 individuals and 345 valid responses that focuses on religious and cultural factors influencing the consumer perception and adoption of Islamic banking within Nigeria. Results of the study reveals that religious belief and cultural norms are significant factors in adopting Islamic banking in Nigeria. Respondents had shows impressive interest toward the adoption when its aligned with both religious and cultural norms.

Abbas and Rehman (2023) have conducted a joint study that focuses on the impact of complexity and service quality on offering Islamic banking products and services in Pakistan. This study uses a quantitative survey method to analyze responses from 400 respondents. The findings reveal that perceived complexity had a negative effect on the adoption of Islamic banking in Pakistan, while service quality positively influenced it.

2.5.1 Trends and Patterns

Islamic banking has grown significantly in regions with strong regulatory frameworks. In addition, the community trust and consciousness remain key drivers of adoption while Afghanistan lags due to economic instability and weak financial regulations, social support and community endorsement increase the adoption. Lastly, service and quality, along with convenience, matter as much as Sharia-Compliance.

2.6 Gaps in the Literature

Most of the studies have used a quantitative approach, and limited research on this topic has been conducted through a qualitative approach with a questionnaire, resulting in triangulation. In addition, the current studies have mostly used TRA and UTUAT theories for the foundation of research.

Most current studies focus on GCC and Southeast Asia, leaving Afghanistan under-researched, with a lack of empirical data on customer preferences and market demand for Islamic banking in Afghanistan. In addition, Insufficient qualitative research on consumer sentiment and institutional challenges in Afghanistan Islamic finance sector.

2.7 Contribution of The Research

The aim of this study is to present a factual data regarding the barriers and potential pathways toward the adoption of Islamic banking. This includes the evaluation of the consumers perception and attitude through the two theories, which are TBP and TRA. In addition to this, conducting in-depth qualitative interviews with bank professionals and questionnaire from 25 consumers will help create a triangulation and increase the validation of the forthcoming themes and or variables.

In contrast to earlier research, this study will focus on Afghanistan post-2021, using qualitative approaches, which offer comprehensive insights into institutional, consumer perception, and regulatory issues. It will collect information through interviews and a questionnaire from 25 consumers to validate themes and increase information intake.

2.8 Organization, Summary, and Integration of Research

This literature review incorporates key theories, TBP and TRA, empirical studies, and gaps in the literature to create a foundation for investigating the barriers and potential pathways for the adoption of Islamic banking in Afghanistan. The study's theoretical and practical aspects will ensure a comprehensive analysis of how Islamic banking can shape a sustained adoption and financial stability. It will also remain an educational resource for the public to increase their awareness of Islamic banking.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction to Research Methodology

This study will investigate the barriers and potential pathways for an enhanced adoption of Islamic banking in Afghanistan. A qualitative approach has been selected to conduct this study, which enables an in-depth exploration from both the consumers and bankers perspectives. It will shed light on what the barriers and the potential pathways are that can increase the adoption in Afghanistan, which shall lead to a sustainable financial sector that is aligned with Islamic beliefs and Sharia-Compliance. This methodology is consistent with the research questions, allowing contextual analysis of the subject.

3.2 Research Design

3.2.1 Qualitative Research Approach

This study will use a qualitative research design, focusing on semi-structured interviews with bank professionals. In addition, a closed-ended and open-ended questionnaire will be used to create a triangulation to increase validation of the themes, patterns, and interpretation of the data. Therefore, this questionnaire is not used for quantitative analysis.

3.2.2 Justification for the Qualitative Approach

This study aims mainly to explore the qualitative approach, the attitude, and experience of the consumers from their own perspective and from those who are working in these institutions

and offering products and services on a daily basis. According to Creswell (2013), qualitative approach is effective when analyzing social phenomena from the viewpoint of themselves. This allows the receipt of rich data to understand the patterns and themes of barriers and potential pathways that would allow an enhanced adoption of Islamic banking in Afghanistan. In addition, besides the semi-structured interviews, a questionnaire with closed-ended questions for understanding the audience group and demographics, and open-ended questions for understanding their belief will be used to triangulate the data. The open-ended responses provide insights into beliefs and expectations, helping to validate and contextualize the interview data (Caron, 2019). As a result, we will understand the current barriers that influence the consumer perception and attitude toward using or not using Islamic banking over conventional banking, and their expectations.

3.3 Data Collection Methods

Data is collected through semi-structured interviews from 10 participants who are currently working in the banking sector and are involved with offering similar products and services daily, and in addition to this, closed and open-ended questionnaires were conducted with 25 consumers, including Islamic banks and conventional banks.

3.4 Sampling Strategy & Size

The purposive sampling has been used in order to select the participants for interviews, and with direct experience in Islamic Banking, a questionnaire was distributed to the public. This ensures that data from the interviews is relevant to the study, and the questionnaire is another validation of it for creating a triangulation and enriching the data for a stronger finding and output.

In total, ten interviews were conducted, and data saturation was achieved at this point, as no new themes or significant insights emerged from the final interviews, indicating that the core patterns and perspectives had been adequately captured (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006)

3.5 Data Analysis Technique and Process

Thematic analysis is used within this research to identify key patterns from the participant responses. The process is initiated with transcribing interviews from oral to written text manually and followed by coding responses via NVivo software, which means, identify recurring words and phrases and ideas and classifying them under themes that represent the main idea and lastly, interpretation of the themes to draw meaningful conclusion.

Figure 2: Data Analysis Flowchart

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

3.5.1 Interviews Questions & Consent

The following is the consent form that has been distributed to all participants and following the consent form are the interview questions.

Figure 3: Interview Consent Form

Interview Consent Form

Research Title:
Barriers and Pathways for Enhancing Islamic Banking Adoption in Afghanistan: A Qualitative Study

Researcher:
Mohammad Shahid Akseer
MBA Candidate, American University of Afghanistan

Purpose of the Study
You are invited to participate in a research study aimed at understanding the barriers and pathways for the adoption of Islamic banking in Afghanistan. Your insights as a banking professional will contribute valuable knowledge to this field.

Participation Details

- Participation is voluntary.
- The interview will last approximately 30–45 minutes.
- You may decline to answer any question or withdraw at any point.
- With your permission, the interview may be audio recorded for accuracy.

Confidentiality
All information you provide will be kept strictly confidential. No identifying information will appear in the final report. Data will be used solely for academic purposes and stored securely.

Consent Statement
By signing this form, you acknowledge that you:

- Understand the purpose of the research.
- Agree to participate voluntarily.
- Consent to the recording of the interview (if applicable).
- Understand your right to withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Participant Name: _____

Participant Signature: _____

Date: _____

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

1. Can you briefly explain your role and experience with Islamic banking products in Afghanistan?
2. What are the main barriers your bank faces in offering Islamic finance products?
3. Are there challenges related to Islamic banking product development or Shariah compliance?
4. How does the current political and economic situation affect Islamic banking operations?
5. In your opinion, what should regulators or the government do to promote Islamic banking in Afghanistan?
6. What strategies would you recommend for overcoming operational and financial challenges?

3.5.2 Closed & Open-Ended Questionnaires

1. Gender
2. Age
3. Education Level
4. Occupation
5. How familiar are you with Islamic Banking
6. What Islamic Banking Services are you aware of?
7. What factors encourages you to use Islamic Banking Products and Services?
8. What challenges or barriers have you faced (or heard about) in using Islamic Banking Services?
9. What recommendations do you have to improve Islamic Banking services in Afghanistan?

3.6 Business Profile

Table 1: Demographics of Ten Interview Participants

ID	Occupation	Education Level	Sector
P1	Bank Manager	Masters Degree	Banking
P2	Islamic Finance Consultant	Masters Degree	Banking
P3	Central Bank Official	Bachelors Degree	Banking
P4	Branch Manager	Bachelors Degree	Banking
P5	Islamic Banking Trainer	Masters Degree	Banking
P6	Senior Risk Manager	Masters Degree	Banking
P7	Operations Manager	Masters Degree	Banking
P8	Shariah Advisory Board Member	PhD	Banking
P9	Product Development Officer	Bachelors Degree	Banking
P10	Regulator (De Afghanistan Bank Official)	Bachelors Degree	Banking

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

In addition, the following is the business profile of those who have participated in the questionnaire based on the information received.

Table 2: Demographics of Survey (Questionnaire) Participants

ID	Gender	Age	Education Level	Occupation
P11	Female	18	Bachelor	Student
P12	Male	38	Master or above	Student
P13	Female	19	High School	Un-Employed
P14	Male	45	Bachelor	Business Owner
P15	Female	27	Master or above	Self-Employed
P16	Male	21	High School	Teacher
P17	Female	20	Bachelor	Student
P18	Male	28	Master or above	Student
P19	Female	22	High School	Un-Employed
P20	Male	49	Bachelor	Business Owner
P21	Female	31	Master or above	NGO Worker
P22	Male	27	Bachelor	Teacher
P23	Female	25	Bachelor	Student
P24	Male	34	Master or above	Student
P25	Female	29	Bachelor	Engineer
P26	Male	39	Bachelor	Business Owner
P27	Female	37	Master or above	Self-Employed
P28	Male	26	Bachelor	Teacher
P29	Female	22	Bachelor	Student
P30	Male	38	Master or above	Student

P31	Female	35	Bachelor	Teacher
P32	Male	42	Bachelor	Business Owner
P33	Female	28	Master or above	Un-Employed
P34	Male	20	Secondary	Un-Employed
P35	Female	25	Bachelor	Student

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

The following paragraphs provides information on two main categories of themes, the initial five themes are related to the research question number one (barriers) and the final five themes are related to the research question number two (potential pathways). Some of the themes might correspond to both research questions if checked against positive or negative responses however, to draw a clear conclusion, they have been put individually.

Table 3: Frequency Table

Frequency Table													
#	Theme	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	Total	%
RQ1	Regulatory & Legal Challenges	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	7	10.77
RQ1	Shariah Compliance & Governance	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	6	9.23
RQ1	Low Public Awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	x	8	12.31
RQ1	Operational and Product Limitations	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	7	10.77
RQ1	Political & Economic Instability	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	5	7.69
RQ2	Education and Awareness Strategies	✓	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	✓	6	12.31
RQ2	Strengthening Regulation and Oversight	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	6	9.23
RQ2	Innovation and Product Development	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	6	10.77
RQ2	Institutional Capacity Building	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	6	9.23
RQ2	Digital and Operational Efficiency	✓	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	✓	✓	x	5	7.69

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

Research Question 1: What obstacles do consumers in Afghanistan encounter when receiving Islamic banking products and services?

Theme 1: Regulatory and Legal Challenges

The participants of both interviews and the survey have expressed strong concern related to the regulatory and legal environment that surrounds Islamic banking in Afghanistan. This shows a lack of a well-defined, clear, and comprehensive legal framework to support the sector. This also creates hesitation among consumers and institutions for the adoption of Islamic banking.

Quotes from Participants:

1. A lack of a unified regulatory framework makes it difficult to promote Islamic banking. - Senior Islamic Banking Manager - Participant 1
2. Regulations are too general, not specific to Islamic finance. - - Participant 2
3. Shariah-compliant products face challenges due to inconsistent regulations. - Branch Manager- Participant 4
4. The regulatory environment does not fully support the growth of Islamic banking. – – Participant 5
5. We need to align financial regulations with Islamic finance standards. – Shariah Advisory Board Member – Participant 8
6. There's a lack of understanding among regulators about Islamic finance. – De Afghanistan Bank Official - Participant 10
7. Afghanistan lacks comprehensive Islamic banking laws. – – Participant 3

Theme 2: Shariah Compliance and Governance Issues

The participant feedback states two main issues regarding sharia compliance and governance, both of which stressed the lack of local qualified sharia experts, raising the trust issue among the consumers. These two interconnected issues impact the consumer and change the consumers attitude toward conventional banking.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Insufficient product innovation and lack of Shariah experts. - Participant 1
2. Absence of a national Islamic finance strategy. - Participant 10
3. Difficulty in aligning products with Shariah law. – Participant 9
4. There is a need for stronger governance on Shariah compliance. – Participant 4
5. Weak Shariah governance frameworks. – Participant 8
6. Yes, Regular audits on Shariah compliance will help improve trust. – Participant 7

Theme 3: Low Public Awareness and Misconceptions

The responses from both categories have noticed an intense lack of awareness and misconception, one of the participant noted that consumers sometime confuses Islamic banking with conventional banking which shows a lack of understanding and awareness on how the product and services that are offered by Islamic banking are different in structure and purpose. With a total mentions of 17, the carries the weight of second items in the barriers category.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Yes, customers confuse Islamic banking with conventional products. - Participant 1
2. Yes, many think Islamic banking is more expensive. – Participant 2
3. Customers lack understanding of profit-loss sharing. – Participant 3

4. Educational campaigns targeting the public will increase awareness. - Participant 5
5. We need to work on increasing public trust through education. - Participant 4
6. Public awareness about Islamic finance is key to market expansion. Participant 7
7. Islamic finance products are not fully understood by the public. Participant 8
8. Awareness programs should address the ethical principles of Islamic banking. Participant 9

Theme 4: Operational and Product Limitations

The participants have noted the operational and product limitations, which include operational inefficiency and a lack of enough products/services, or they are not meeting the consumers needs. With a total of 20 mentions combined in the interview and survey respondents, this carries the highest weight of barriers..

Quotes from Participants:

1. Limited product variety in Islamic finance is a major operational challenge. - Participant 2
2. High service charges remain a problem for Islamic finance. – Participant 3
3. Operational processes need to be simplified for customers. – Participant 5
4. Shariah-compliant products should be more widely available. – Participant 4
5. Training staff on Islamic finance operations is a necessity. Participant 6
6. The current product offerings are not sufficient to meet customer demand. - Participant 7
7. Operational limitations slow down growth in the sector. - Participant 9

Theme 5: Political and Economical Instability

The participants have noted the negative impact of the current economic and political climate on the growth of Islamic banking in Afghanistan. During the review of respondents replies,

it was also noted that financial institutions are afraid of launching various products within struggling economies.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Political instability disrupts the growth of Islamic finance. - Participant 1
2. Economic instability creates challenges in attracting investors. - Participant 6
3. Economic challenges impact the ability to offer Shariah-compliant finance products. - Participant 3
4. Political unrest limits access to banking services. - Participant 9
5. Unstable economic conditions harm the growth of Islamic banking. - Participant 10

Table 4: Five Themes Representing RQ1 with all of its Mentions

#	Theme	Interview Mentions	Survey Mentions	Total Mentions	Percentage
1	Regulatory & Legal Challenges	7	8	15	20.55
2	Shariah Compliance & Governance	6	7	13	17.81
3	Low Public Awareness	8	9	17	23.29
4	Operational and Product Limitations	7	13	20	27.40
5	Political & Economic Instability	5	3	8	10.96

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

Figure 4: Five Themes Representing RQ1 with Responses from both Interview and Survey

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

This chart further clarifies and clearly shows the number of respondents noting each theme and it is useful to understand the weight of each theme if analyzed individually. 13 is the maximum mention in this category which is noted under the Operational and product limitation

Figure 5: Five Themes Representing RQ1 in a Pie Chart

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

This pie chart is showing the initial five themes that are related to the first research questions and are showing all the barriers that respondents from both categories (Interview and Survey) have noted. Though, the number of survey respondent is higher than the interview however, it doesn't change or effect the outcome as it is applied across all five themes.

Research Question 2: How can banking institutions in Afghanistan enhance the adoption and effectiveness of Islamic finance products?

Theme 6: Education and Awareness Strategies

Considering that, Public Awareness is being noted as the higher percentage in recommendations to improve the adoption of Islamic banking. The participants of both survey and interview suggest launching literacy campaigns through religious leaders, schools and government to endorse banks that provides Islamic banking products and services.

Quotes from Participants:

1. We need to educate the public on the advantages of Islamic banking. - Participant 1
2. Awareness campaigns are essential to spread knowledge about Shariah-compliant banking.
- Participant 4
3. Increased financial literacy is necessary to increase market share. - Participant 5
4. A long-term commitment to public awareness can build trust. - Participant 6
5. Campaigns targeting youth can have a lasting impact. - Participant 7
6. Public awareness programs should address the ethical aspects of Islamic finance. -
Participant 10
7. Improved understanding through seminars and workshops is critical. - Participant 2

Theme 7: Strengthening Regulation and Oversight

Participants from both groups emphasized institutional reforms and technological improvements to strengthen the Islamic Banking sector. The participant from the interview group stated that a national sharia board is needed to oversee and ensure a consistent policy is maintained across the country for standardization and consistency across the industry. In addition, the other participant from the survey mentioned that expanding online accessibility is important. Together, both will result in enhanced oversight and strengthen the regulations.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Regulations need to be updated to support Islamic finance growth. - Participant 4
2. More transparency in regulations would increase trust. - Participant 6
3. Regulatory bodies should have clearer guidelines for Islamic banking. - Participant 7
4. The oversight should be more focused on compliance with Shariah principles. - Participant 8
5. A regulatory framework tailored to Islamic finance will enhance market stability. - Participant 9
6. Better coordination between financial regulators and Islamic finance experts is essential. - Participant 10

Theme 8: Innovation and Product Development

The participants from both groups have emphasized product and system innovation while maintaining and considering that all products and services are within Sharia compliance. A participant from the Interviews suggested testing new products on a pilot basis while ensuring that

the digital banking product is enhanced so that consumers can easily explore the nature of all products and use them with their fingertips.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Encourage more product innovation in Islamic banking. – Participant 2
2. We need more products that cater to different customer segments. - Participant 4
3. Pilot testing new products will help assess market demand. - Participant 5
4. Developing flexible products is important for broader adoption. - Participant 7
5. New products must meet customer needs in a competitive market. - Participant 8
6. More diverse product offerings will boost market penetration. - Participant 10

Theme 9: Institutional Capacity Building

The participants emphasized the importance of capacity building to support and create a sustainable path for continuous growth. The interview participants stressed the importance of collaboration with international financial institutions that aim to share knowledge and increase local expertise, which will ultimately expose the banking sector to global competition and best practices. The interview respondents mentioned Qatar, Malaysia, and Indonesia as examples of role models. Similarly, the survey participants mentioned the importance of creating a culture for continuous capacity building and that the organization must invest in their local staff for capacity building.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Capacity building through international partnerships is essential. - Participant 1
2. Training programs for Shariah-compliant professionals should be expanded. - Participant 2
3. There is a need for more Islamic finance expertise. - Participant 6

4. Developing a strong institutional framework will support growth. - Participant 7
5. Collaboration with international financial institutions will improve capacity. - Participant 8
6. Building local expertise is essential for sustainable growth. - Participant 9

Theme 10: Digital and Operational Efficiency

The participants have consistently emphasized the need for digital infrastructure reform of financial institutions in Afghanistan. This will create a number of plus points for the financial institutions, such as wider accessibility, customer convenience, operational cost reduction, faster service delivery, and increased transparency and trust.

Quotes from Participants:

1. Digital platforms should be introduced to facilitate Islamic banking services. - Participant 1
2. Digital solutions for Islamic finance are the future. - Participant 4
3. Automating Islamic banking processes will increase efficiency. - Participant 5
4. Online platforms should be developed for wider customer reach. - Participant 9
5. Digital transformation is crucial for the long-term growth of Islamic finance. - Participant 8

Table 5: Five Themes Representing RQ2 with all of its Mentions

#	Theme	Interview Mentions	Survey Mentions	Total Mentions	Percentage (%)
1	Education & Awareness Strategies	8	20	28	26.42%
2	Strengthening Regulation & Oversight	6	13	19	17.92%

3	Innovation & Product Development	7	17	24	22.64%
4	Institutional Capacity Building	6	10	16	15.09%
5	Digital & Operational Efficiency	5	14	19	17.92%

Source: Developed by Author of the Research.

Figure 6: Five Themes Representing RQ2 with Responses from Both Interviews and Survey

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

Figure 7: Five Themes Representing RQ2 in a Pie Chart

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

CHAPTER FIVE.

DISCUSSION, RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Overview of Findings

The main objective of this study was to explore the consumer barrier to adopting the Islamic banking in Afghanistan and to explore the potential pathways that would enhance the adoption. This study is guided under the following two research questions.

1. What obstacles do consumers in Afghanistan encounter when receiving Islamic banking products and services?
2. How can banking institutions in Afghanistan enhance the adoption and effectiveness of Islamic finance products?

From the initial data received from 10 interviews and 25 survey participants, 10 distinct themes were drawn as final findings, classified under each related research question. The table below summarizes each relevant research questions themes, sub-codes, and frequency.

5.2 Interpretation of Findings

Research Question 1: Barriers to Islamic Banking

5.2.1 Regulatory and Legal Challenges:

Perhaps the largest hurdle to consumer access to Islamic banking in Afghanistan is the lack of well-developed and complete legal structures. The participants noted that the lack of national shariah board, the ambiguity of Islamic financial product regulations and the inconsistent application of regulation have given rise to widespread consumer confusion and lack of trust. Because there is no official backing and large guidance, the majority of the customers dislike the

Islamic Banking, not knowing if the product being provided is Shariah compliant. It agrees with the findings of Naseri and Sharofiddin (2021), which have highlighted the provision of government backing and explanations by laws to enhance the confidence level of customers as well as acceptability. Further, Yaseen and Kamran (2019) confirmed that in Pakistan, consumers are deterred from deviating conventional banks owing to disbelief in the legitimacy and consistency of Islamic banking regulations. In Afghanistan, with an Islamic heritage highly rooted, the public is keen to using Islamic banking but are being retrained due to unclear regulations and lack of trusted oversight.

This is precisely the essence of alienation from Islamic banking that most Afghan consumers experience. They are not refusing unwillingly, but they do not have a guaranteed legal option and a noble governing body to rely on who will guarantee Shariah compliance. Absence of a standardized, dignified regulation system discourages even those customers, who would utilize Islamic banking in place of their religion, and the deterrence is equivalent to zero action. Addressing this fundamental problem is essential for building consumer trust and initiating adoption.

5.2.2 Shariah Compliance and Governance Issues

Doubts regarding the Shariah-compliance of products due to insufficient qualified scholars, poor governance structures, and a lack of transparency were often expressed by respondents. This is consistent with Yaseen and Kamran's (2019) observation of the same concerns among consumers in Pakistan.

In a country where nearly everyone is Muslim, trust in religious authenticity is non-negotiable. Weak internal governance compromises that trust. This is not merely a technical

issue—it is emotional and spiritual to Afghan consumers. Robust national Shariah governance is essential.

5.2.3 Low Public Awareness and Misconceptions

Interviews and survey responses alike mirrored a dire lack of understanding of Islamic finance principles. The majority of consumers cannot distinguish between Islamic and conventional products. This confirms previous research by Mahdzan et al. (2017), who established poor literacy and misconceptions as barriers to adoption, even in more developed Islamic markets like Malaysia.

I consider this barrier as the most manageable. Unlike regulatory reform, which is tardy, awareness can be created with immediate effect through focused outreach. Working via religious leaders and schools could potentially effect change within a period of months.

5.2.4 Operational and Product Limitations

Respondents indicated that inadequate product range, outdated services, and lack of digital channels discourage customer adoption. These findings echo Abbas and Rehman (2023), who established that complexity and reduced service quality discourage the usage of Islamic banking. Even where Islamic banking is available, product limitations render it unappealing.

From my personal experience working with Islamic bank customers, it's clear that customers don't just want "Islamic" labels—they want usability, modern technology, and choice. Failure to modernize will render even the most Shariah-compliant products irrelevant.

5.2.5 Political and Economic Instability

Respondents viewed ongoing political instability and poor economic conditions as significant dampeners to investment and banking sector expansion. These structural barriers echo findings

by Beck et al. (2013), who explained that macroeconomic stability is critical for the growth of any financial sector, particularly in post-conflict nations.

While some factor are largely beyond the control of banks, strategic partnership with NGOs or international Islamic finance institution can mitigate some of the effects of instability.

Research Question 2: Pathways and Strategies for Adoption

5.2.6 Education and Awareness Strategies

Respondents strongly favored targeted literacy campaigns, particularly with the inclusion of religious scholars, schools, and media. This aligns with Naseri and Sharofiddin (2021), where religiosity and product knowledge were emphasized in the adoption of Islamic banking. Public education was also recommended in the Nigerian context by Osaretin (2023), where religious and cultural awareness led to higher consumer acceptance.

Knowledge is the door opener to mass adoption. Once Afghans know that Islamic banking is aligned with both their faith and financial interests, behavior will change. Campaigns by trusted community leaders are the most credible agents of change.

5.2.7 Strengthening Regulation and Oversight

Participants were in general agreement that an independent, national Shariah board and Islamic finance specialist regulatory body would standardize practice and build confidence. Afghanistan government must create a centralized Islamic finance board that is in close association with the central bank and religious scholars. Otherwise, the industry will continue to be in a state of ambiguity, which will reduce its scalability and public acceptance.

5.2.8 Innovation and Product Development

Diversification and customization of products to better respond to consumer needs were suggested by respondents, an argument also made by Boubker et al. (2021) in their study of Moroccan micro-entrepreneurs. Afghanistan can also benefit from the reproduction of tested models in Qatar and Malaysia.

Localized product development, I believe, is a must. Agriculture-based murabaha, micro-mudarabah, and ijara leasing models with features that have flexibility for rural people would provide Afghans with utility as well as moral assurance.

5.2.9 Institutional Capacity Building

Staff training, Shariah-compliant certification programs, and academic curriculum development were stressed by participants. Capacity building takes time, but the lack of qualified personnel is already limiting service delivery today. I suggest starting partnerships with foreign Islamic finance institutions to speed up the development of local personnel.

5.2.10 Digital and Operational Efficiency

Respondents also pointed out digital channels as central to service expansion, convenience, and transparency. In today's Afghanistan, where mobility and access are restricted in most areas of the country, digital solutions can bridge the gap. Online onboarding, mobile applications, and e-wallets will make Islamic finance more inclusive and efficient.

5.3 Implications for Theory and Practice

5.3.1 Theoretical Contributions

The implications of this study make a significant contribution to existing theoretical models such as the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which focus primarily on individual attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioral control in the prediction of consumer behavior. While both theories have been instrumental in financial behavior explanation in other contexts, the evidence in this Afghan case specifies five special systemic barriers that are not adequately reflected in those models: Regulatory and Legal Challenges, Shariah Compliance and Governance Issues, Low Public Awareness and Misconceptions, Operational and Product Limitations, and Political and Economic Instability.

These barriers are institutional and structural in nature instead of being purely behavioral or psychological issues. TPB, for instance, assumes intention-based behavior under control and social norms, but in Afghanistan, consumers do not even get the opportunity to form an intention due to the absence of legal infrastructure or product availability. Similarly, the TRA assumes decision-making based on rational evaluation of consequences, but in Afghanistan, decisions are more likely to be made on the basis of imperfect information, religious belief, or fear of non-compliance with Islamic law.

This addresses a basic theoretical flaw from the researcher's perspective. The use of Islamic banking by Afghan consumers is not just a question of behavior but also of institution and context. Afghan consumers are willing, even keen, to use Islamic financial services if they are Shariah-compliant—but systemic weaknesses constrain their ability to do so. What is needed is a broader theoretical framework that integrates behavioral intent with structural possibility. Therefore, this study not only confirms elements of TRA and TPB but also extends them by

adding five contextual variables that need to be taken into account in post-conflict, religiously driven, underbanked communities such as Afghanistan. The following diagram shows the research model.

Figure 8: Research Model

Source: Developed by Author of the research.

5.3.2 Practical Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study have key practical implications for Afghan communities, institutions, and the government. One of the easiest and most urgent necessities is to launch large-scale campaigns through social media, mosques, religious leaders, and community gatherings to educate people on shariah-compliant finance, its benefits, and distinctions with other conventional financial products and services. This will dispel misunderstandings and establish trust.

In addition to awareness, Islamic banking must innovate and diversify its products and services according to the market's needs, focusing on agriculture, study loans, microenterprise,

and other SME. This includes Murabaha agriculture finance, car finance, house finance, etc., while strictly following Shariah Law.

Human capital is another significant implication that needs to be focused on. Institutions need to train their staff to provide accurate information, which will lead to better customer interaction and consumer satisfaction. Staff training programs include international certification, which will boost the institution's credibility in consumers' eyes.

There is also a need for a national Sharia board and strong oversight to ensure that the products and services offered by institutions are in accordance with Islamic Law. This will remove consumer concerns regarding the transparency of the products and services and ensure that they are receiving services that are fully in accordance with Shariah.

Lastly, the digitalization must be embraced. There is a need for greater mobile banking, online registration, and e-wallet services which are important to reach distant customers and consumers and make it easier for them to take study all the products and services and make an informed decision and to be able to adopt the banking without the need to visit the branch.

5.3.3 Policy Implications and Recommendations

A national sharia board to formulate, implement and oversight a single policy to ensure the customer trust is received with dedicated units in the central bank. In addition to this, the government needs to subsidize the technical support to the banks that are offering Islamic banking products and services and to promote them through government funded large scale campaigns.

To enhance the adoption, the university should integrate the Islamic finance education in the secondary and university levels. This will build the future generation that is financially literate. In addition to this, the government should arrange financial literacy programs that includes

Islamic Finances in collaboration with religious leaders, civil society organizations and location institutions across the country. Such initiatives will ensure a consistent information flow and will result in increase of financial literacy level.

Lastly, the policy makers must ensure that digital infrastructure is developed and that it supports the Islamic banking operations. The regulatory body must ensure that all the banks are included in the national financial inclusion strategy via dedicated funding to ensure the outreach via digital channels.

5.4 Limitations of the Study & Suggestion to Address

The limitations of the research exploring the challenges and barriers to the adoption of Islamic banking in Afghanistan, and potential pathways to fill this gap is the use of a qualitative method, the findings are not generalizable across different regions and communities in Afghanistan. The experience and views gathered may not be those of the rural or underdeveloped province consumers, whose access to Islamic financial institutions is limited or nil therefore, I suggest the with the use quantitative method, more accurate data could be gathered.

The study also carries a geographic and institutional focus, restricting the sampling. Participants were primarily represented from areas where Islamic banking facilities are at least partially available. Hence, the study could potentially not capture the full extent of challenges faced by individuals in unbanked Islamic places, where challenges could be quite different. The information also strongly relied on self-reported situations through questionnaires and interviews, which are susceptible to over-reporting, under-reporting, or a proclivity to provide socially or religiously acceptable answers. The future research should engage participants from the rural areas and from the areas where this service is entirely not available.

The study also takes a snapshot of sentiment at a specific point in time. With the fast-changing political and economic climate of Afghanistan, consumer sentiment and institutional policy will vary over time. A longitudinal approach could provide more powerful insights into how Islamic banking take-up changes as an evolving response to altering governance, digital infrastructure, and financial inclusion initiatives.

The operational and digital efficiency were noted as important themes, this study did not cover an in-depth examination of the current digital banking infrastructure or its macroeconomic environment. These two factors might significantly influence youth and urban consumers who are more inclined toward digital financial services. The future research should focus on exploring this two factor and understanding their role and importance, and examining how these two can shape and impact consumer behavior.

Last, the theoretical underpinnings of the research, based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), are primarily focused on people's attitudes, subjective norms, and intentions. However, several recognized barriers in Afghanistan, such as ambiguity in the legal environment, low institutional trust, and inadequate governance, fall outside the domain of these behavior theories. While such research implies a broadening of these theories with the discovery of new institutional constraints, further research may be supplemented by the inclusion of more in-depth models incorporating structural and environmental factors in post-conflict financial systems.

5.5 Conclusion

This study explored the current consumer barrier and potential pathways toward the adoption of the Islamic banking in Afghanistan, despite a strong cultural and regions inclination of consumers toward Shariah-compliant financial services. The study reveals that the consumers

are not resistant to using Islamic banking but are they are held back by a range of challenges that restrict their knowledge, access, and confidence in the system. These are the absence of clear and consistent guidelines, doubt about Shariah compliance, limited public awareness, inadequacy of available and diversified financial products, and concerns over political and economic instability.

While traditional behavioral models such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) accounted for individual motivation and intention, this research identifies that the majority of consumers are not even able to make it to the decision stage due to structural and institutional barriers. Their behavior is guided not only by personal attitudes or social pressure, but also by unclear rules, untrained bank staff, outdated service models, and limited access to correct information. All these customer-side problems call for a better understanding of their lived experience, especially the urban consumers.

However, the study also points to solutions that are within reach. It is more likely that consumers will accept Islamic banking if they are properly informed, if the services are convenient and tailored to their daily needs, and there is a well-established system that ensures transparency and religious authenticity. Public education via channels of trust in the community, electronic banking services, open Shariah regulation, and responsive product design are all viable steps that can bridge the gap between current consumer interest and actual participation.

Lastly, this research shows that Islamic Banking holds great promise of sustainable economic development however, realizing its full potential will require a coordinated effort among all stakeholders with a commitment to full transparency and customer oriented approach that is driven by both faith and functionality.

REFERENCES

- Islamic Financial Services Board [IFSB]. (2023). Annual Report 2023. In Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB-AR2023). Islamic Financial Services Board. Retrieved February 10, 2025, from <https://www.ifsb.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/IFSB-AR2023-Gray.pdf>
- Staff, J. (2022, March 21). Afghanistan dispatch: the Taliban want to replace the conventional banking system with Islamic banking. JURIST - News. <https://www.jurist.org/news/2022/03/afghanistan-dispatch-the-taliban-want-to-replace-the-conventional-banking-system-with-islamic-banking>
- UNDP. (2021). Afghanistan Socio-Economic Outlook 2021-2022: Averting a Basic Needs Crisis. <https://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2022-05/UNDP-AFG-Afghanistan-Socio-Economic-Outlook-2021-2022%20%281%29.pdf>
- World Bank Open Data. (2023). World Bank Open Data. Retrieved April 20, 2025, from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/>
- World Bank Group. (2025, February 9). Afghanistan: Economy shows modest growth after two years of severe contraction, but recovery remains fragile. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2024/12/04/afghanistan-economy-shows-modest-growth-after-two-years-of-severe-contraction-but-recovery-remains-fragile>
- Afghanistan population (2025) - Worldometer. (n.d.). Worldometer. <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/afghanistan-population/>
- Muslim Population by Country 2025. (n.d.). <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/muslim-population-by-country>

First Islamic Bank In Afghanistan Opens For Business. (2018, April 25). Tolo News.

<https://tolonews.com/business/first-islamic-bank-afghanistan-opens-business#:~:text=IBA%20is%20now%20the%20only,by%20Azizi%20Bank%20in%202009.>

World Bank Group. (2022). The Global FiNDEX 2021: Interactive Executive Summary Visualization. In World Bank.

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/globalfindex/interactive-executive-summary-visualization>

Wikipedia contributors. (2025, April 23). Islamic banking and finance - Wikipedia.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islamic_banking_and_finance

Islamic Bank of Afghanistan. (n.d.). <https://www.ibafg.com/murabaha>

Nugraha, K., Arief, M., Abdinagoro, S. B., & Heriyati, P. (2022). Factors influencing bank customers orientations toward Islamic banks: Indonesian banking perspective. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912506>

Naseri, K., & Sharofiddin, A. (2021). *Empirical study on adoption of Islamic banking system using quantitative method: A case study of Afghanistan*. *Turkish Journal of Islamic Economics*, 8(2), 571–595. <https://doi.org/10.26414/A169>

Yaseen, Z., & Kamran, S. (2019). *Exploring the impediments faced by the banking customers to adopt Islamic banking services in Pakistan*. *Journal of Islamic Business and Management*, 9(2), 297–310. <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://jibm.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/1-2->

[3.pdf#:~:text=1%20Exploring%20the%20Impediments%20faced,of%20Islamic%20banking%20services%20remains](#)

Boubker, O., Douayri, K., & Ouajdouni, A. (2021). *Factors affecting intention to adopt Islamic financing: Evidence from Morocco*. *MethodsX*, 8, 101523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2021.101523>

Mahdzan, N. S., Zainudin, R., & Au, S. F. (2017). The adoption of Islamic banking services in Malaysia. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 10(3), 384–406. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMEFM-06-2016-0070>

Osaretin, I. A. (2023). Perception and adoption of Islamic banking: Exploring factors influencing consumer behavior in Nigeria. *Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance*, 40(2), 75–90. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/37743773>

Abbas, S., & Rehman, M. (2023). Analysis of customers adoption of Islamic banking in Pakistan: The effects of complexity and service quality. *Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance*, 40(1), 45–60. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369728899>

Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications. [https://books.google.com.qa/books?hl=en&lr=&id=DLbBDQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Creswell,+J.+W.+\(2013\).+Qualitative+inquiry+and+research+design:+Choosing+among+five+approaches+\(3rd+ed.\).+SAGE+Publications&ots=ir63fLTVw&sig=uC4E5ta-VLkCI103xpYommRuN8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Creswell%2C%20J.%20W.](https://books.google.com.qa/books?hl=en&lr=&id=DLbBDQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Creswell,+J.+W.+(2013).+Qualitative+inquiry+and+research+design:+Choosing+among+five+approaches+(3rd+ed.).+SAGE+Publications&ots=ir63fLTVw&sig=uC4E5ta-VLkCI103xpYommRuN8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Creswell%2C%20J.%20W.)

[%20\(2013\).%20Qualitative%20inquiry%20and%20research%20design%3A%20Choosing%20among%20five%20approaches%20\(3rd%20ed.\).%20SAGE%20Publications&f=false](#)

Caron, J. A. (2019). Triangulation in qualitative research: Theory and practice. In R. Coe, M. Waring, L. V. Hedges, & J. Arthur (Eds.), *Research methods and methodologies in education* (2nd ed., pp. 146–155). SAGE Publications.
<https://books.google.ca/books?hl=en&lr=&id=pFMIEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Research+methods+and+methodologies+in+education&ots=0W58ViKJM&sig=fF5CZMoBnl6SiJqRXH4i75ijTQ#v=onepage&q=Research%20methods%20and%20methodologies%20in%20education&f=false>

Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field Methods*, 18(1), 59–82.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X05279903>